

A Theory of Colour on the Basis of Molecular Strain.

Part VII. The Effect of Polymembered Ring Formation.

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The present paper is the result of an investigation undertaken in connection with a theory of colour advanced by one of the present authors (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **122**, 1171; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 99), to find out the relative stability of a number of polymembered ring systems derived from the higher dibasic fatty acids, and to compare the depth of colour of a series of dyestuffs containing such rings.

According to the well known "strain theory" of Baeyer, cyclic compounds containing five and six members in the ring should be most stable, while the stability will gradually decrease as this limit is exceeded in either direction. With all the data that are at present available regarding the stability of the ring systems, it can be conclusively proved that though three and four membered rings are quite capable of existence, nevertheless they are unstable, and can be easily ruptured. But the same cannot be said with regard to cyclic compounds containing more than six members in the ring. For instance adipic anhydride, which contains a seven membered ring, has been proved to be a definite entity, while the cases of diphenic anhydride and suberone, containing seven membered rings are particularly well known. By condensing diphenic anhydride with aromatic amino- and hydroxy-compounds, a series of dyestuffs belonging to the pyronine group has been obtained (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 222), the colours of which are so light that there is no doubt about the fact that in these compounds the seven membered ring assumes the character of great stability.

About an eight membered ring, there is at present hardly any definite compound known containing such a ring, though from time to time various authors, in their publications, have assumed the existence of such ring formations. Borsche (*Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 1960)

prepared from azelaic acid a ketone, which he considered to be *cyclooctanone*. Apart from this well known but isolated example, compounds containing eight or more members are very little known. All these data, somewhat scarce and conflicting though they are, clearly show that cyclic compounds containing more than six members are quite capable of formation and existence. If a chain of several carbon atoms is arranged in space, linked with one another by single linkage and with due conformation to their valency directions, it will be seen that instead of a straight line the carbon atoms get arranged in a spiral, with a tendency towards the formation of a complete cycle after every fifth carbon atom. Considered in that light it will be clearly seen that a five membered ring will be the most stable of all when the two ends of the spiral just complete a cycle, and the stability will gradually decrease until it reaches a minimum with the seventh member, when the two ends of the spiral are diametrically opposite to each other. After that the stability will again begin to increase with the eighth and ninth member since the ends of the spiral are tending to complete their second circle, and reach a culmination point again with the tenth member, when the ends are again near to each other.

In order to prove the truth of such a hypothesis, the following five acids, namely adipic, pimelic, suberic, azelaic and sebacic acids, have been condensed with resorcinol and *m*-diethylamidophenol with the formation of the corresponding fluoresceins and rhodamines. The intensity of their colour in solution is inversely proportional to the stability of their ring systems constituting their anhydrides as can be easily seen from the following configuration representing their general formula,

where $R=OH$ or NEt_2 , and x may be anything from 4 to 8. Such a compound on solution in alkali or acid will undergo fission of the lactone ring with the formation of a quinonoid structure and consequent

development of colour (Dutt and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 252 4; Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 120, 1132), thus:

where $R' = O$ or NEt_2Hal .

Therefore it will be clearly seen that the greater the stability of the lactone ring the less will be the colour development and *vice versa*. Actual data that have been obtained with regard to the intensity of colour of this series of compounds, show that they are in perfect accordance with the above supposition. The greatest development is seen in the case of compounds derived from adipic acid while the least is in the cases of azelaic and sebacic acids. Almost all these compounds, in general properties, colour and fluorescence, resemble the corresponding derivatives of succinic and glutaric acids (Dutt and Thorpe, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Resorcinol-adipein.—A mixture of adipic acid (5.5 g.), resorcinol (8.4 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (2 c.c.) was heated at 170-180° for about four hours. The melt was then dissolved in dilute ammonia and precipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid. The resultant precipitate was afterwards crystallised from acetic acid in brown needles, not melting below 286°. Unlike resorcinol-succinein the substance dissolves in alkalis with a dark red colour. The alkaline solutions are very unstable in presence of air. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 4.7. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 69.2; H, 5.1 per cent.).

m-Diethylamidophenol-adipein.—A mixture of *m* diethylamidophenol (6.8 g.), adipic acid (2.9 g.) and a few drops of sulphuric acid was heated at 120-130° for about 20 hours, when the melt completely solidified and a little of it when tested gave a bright pink colour with dilute hydrochloric acid. The powdered melt was washed with water and dilute ammonia, dissolved in dilute hydrochloric

acid and reprecipitated with sodium carbonate. Finally it was crystallised from alcohol in pink needles sintering at 138°. (Found: N, 6.2. $C_{26}H_{34}N_2O_3$ requires N, 6.6 per cent.).

Resorcinol-pimelicin.—This was prepared from pimelic acid and resorcinol in a manner similar to the corresponding compound of adipic acid. It was crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid in glistening brown needles, melting at 164°. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 5.6. $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 69.9; H, 5.5 per cent.).

Resorcinol-subericin.—Suberic acid (1.7 g.) and resorcinol (2.2 g.) were heated together with a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid at 170° for about four hours, when the mixture completely solidified. The powdered product was washed with water and then crystallised from 5% hydrochloric acid in small glistening yellow needles, m. p. 140°. The substance dissolved in alkalis with a deep yellow colour and the solution on dilution showed an intense green fluorescence. (Found: C, 70.0; H, 5.8. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 70.5; H, 5.9 per cent.).

m-Diethylamidophenol-subericin.—This compound was prepared from *m*-diethylamidophenol and suberic acid in a similar way to the corresponding compound of adipic acid. It crystallised from alcohol in dark violet needles, m. p. 147°. (Found: N, 6.1. $C_{28}H_{38}O_3N_2$ requires N, 6.2 per cent.).

Resorcinol-azelaic.—This was prepared from azelaic acid and resorcinol in a similar way to resorcinol-adipic. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in chocolate brown needles melting at 172°. (Found: C, 70.8; H, 6.0. $C_{21}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 71.2; H, 6.04 per cent.).

m-Diethylamidophenol-azelaic.—Prepared from *m*-diethylamidophenol and azelaic acid in a similar way to the corresponding compound from adipic acid. It could not be crystallised. It was obtained from alcohol as a violet-red powder dissolving in dilute hydrochloric acid with a brilliant pink colour, m.p. 126°. (Found: N, 6.0. $C_{29}H_{40}O_3N_2$ requires N, 6.03 per cent.).

Resorcinol-sebacic.—Prepared from sebacic acid and resorcinol in a similar way to resorcinol-adipic. It crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid in glistening yellow needles, sintering at 166°. (Found: C, 71.22; H, 6.1. $C_{22}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, 71.74; H, 6.5 per cent.).

m-Diethylamidophenol-sebacein. — Prepared from *m*-diethylamidophenol and sebacic acid in a similar way to the corresponding adipic acid compound. It could not be crystallised. It was obtained from alcohol as a dark violet powder melting at 142°. (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{30}H_{42}N_2O_3$ requires N, 5.6 per cent.).

Absorption maxima of dyestuffs. (Figures indicate approximate wave-lengths).

Dyes derived from—	Rhodamine type.	Fluorescein type.	
		In alcohol.	In KOH.
Adipic acid	5132	4910	5120
Pimelic „	—	4880	4980
Suberic „	5038	4865	4910
Azelaic „	5038	4823	4880
Sebacic „	5076	4830	4880

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